

Research culture as an important component of creating a new content of competency education

Intigam Jabrailov,

Dr. of Pedagogical sciences, Institute of Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Baku

Keywords: research, culture, competence, education, maintenance, formation, student, principle, form, ways, abilities, teacher

Abstract. The article explains the essence of the concept of research culture, substantiates its role in creating a new content of competency-based education. Research can be considered as one of the key skills.

Experience and research show that the culture of research is important as an important component in creating a new content for competency-based education. In other words, it is very important to pay special attention to the research culture of pupils and students in educational standards, to emphasize the formation of such a culture in students, to substantiate the solution of problems, opportunities and ways with conceptual ideas and concrete provisions.

The article provides scientific analysis and generalizations about the principles of formation of research culture in students, opportunities and ways of organizing work in terms of problems. Commenting on theoretical and practical issues, the author concludes that one of the necessary principles in the formation of a research culture in students is the provision of their scientific thinking or creative-research thinking. Because the objective analysis of any issue, the achievement of the right scientific result is first of all directly related to creative thinking.

Research shows that although there are different approaches to the formation of a culture of research, the essence of the work in terms of the problem is largely the same. The main goal here is to ensure that students have a high level of competence by mastering research qualities and values. Thus, it can be said that a person who is able to work with different sources, analyze, compare, generalize, draw conclusions and evaluate other moral values, in fact, has formed a culture of research.

The formation of a research culture is an ongoing process. First of all, it is important to know where to start. To do this, the student can ask himself the following question: What will be investigated? For what purpose will it be investigated? How will it be investigated? What can be the expected result?

What is the significance of the problem to be investigated? What can be expected from the research? and so on. Asking these questions and thinking about them will help you find the key elements of the research and guide the research in the right direction.

Seminars play an important role in shaping the research culture of students in the learning process. Seminars open a wide range of research opportunities by focusing on the teaching of a specific subject.

Introduction

Innovative approaches in the modern education system are closely related to the development trends of society, integration processes caused by globalization, the need to ensure the future security of mankind, the formation of students as creative, competitive, fair individuals and other issues. In this regard, the problem of the new content of competency-based education is particularly noteworthy. Because the formation of personality depends primarily on the extent to which the content of education meets modern requirements. The content of education should ultimately reflect the personality and qualities of the citizen to be nurtured in the end. That is, what skills should be formed in students at the end of the relevant stages and levels of education?

It is the content of education that should focus on the formation of these skills. Unlike general education, the skills formed in students at the higher education level are broader. Thus, a student studying in one or another specialty must have skills in several areas, such as a future specialist, a professional, for example, a teacher. Teachers' competencies can be divided into three parts:

1) the most basic (general) skills; 2) subject competencies; 3) special skills. [Scientific-theoretical problems of modernization of education (published by IH Jabrailov). Baku, 2015]

General competencies, that is, the most important competencies, can be called key competencies. Because these skills are universal, they are not limited to a specific subject and play a key role in the effectiveness of a teacher's pedagogical activity. Subject competencies guarantee the quality of teaching a particular subject. Special skills are related to the work with students in the most difficult moments, in different situations. This includes work with students involved in inclusive education, gifted children, children with special needs.

The research and leadership skills required by research and information technology can be considered key skills.

As can be seen, research today is a key content component for the effective organization of education. This also gives grounds to say that the issue of application of new technologies is related to the content.

Research culture

Experience and research show that the culture of research is important as an important component in creating a new content for competency-based education. In other words, it is very important to pay special attention to the research culture of pupils and students in educational standards, to emphasize

the formation of such a culture in students, to substantiate the solution of problems, opportunities and ways with conceptual ideas and concrete provisions.

Today's research culture is in fact a valuable skill.

It should be noted that according to the traditional approach, culture is a set of material and spiritual achievements of people in life.

1 According to the modern approach, the view of culture is a bit different. Cultural scientist, prof. FTMammadov writes: "Culture is the second artificial nature, it is all the positives created by human mind, feelings and physical labor. At the same time, it is a historically creative process, a path from chaos and ignorance - the path to knowledge, order, development and prosperity [Mammadov FT Baku, 2016]

It follows that the idea of preserving and improving human life is the basis of cultural development.

Prof. Explaining the concept of culture, FTMammadov approaches it from 3 directions: 1) culture in the scientific sense; 2) culture in the context and 3) culture in the limited and ordinary sense.

2 In the scientific sense, it means the process of understanding and changing nature, man himself and society. In the context, culture is defined as a qualitative characteristic of an event, field of activity, individual and social relations, or the level of development of a person. In the limited and ordinary sense, the concept of culture, mentioned as a third direction, includes language, literature, art, folklore, traditions, cultural heritage, ethical norms. [Mammadov FT Baku, 2016]

Research shows that culture is an indicator of a person's personality, what he is capable of and what qualities he carries. Culture is the spiritual face of man as a person.

Experience shows that among the moral qualities that are important for any researcher, it is important to master his research culture.

The research culture is an integral part of the general culture and reflects a number of specific features.

First of all, it should be noted that everyone who is engaged in research, what is research? must answer the question correctly, get acquainted with the requirements for research, researcher, know the technology of research.

Research is a scientific activity carried out consistently in order to increase scientific knowledge and search for new areas for their application. We need to keep in mind that research can be conducted at different levels and levels of education. Researchers can be pupils, students, teachers, doctoral students and others. If simple requirements (work on a given text, drawing conclusions, etc.) are set for the student's research, in the later stages these requirements become more complex and are aimed at drawing more serious scientific conclusions.

First of all, it is important for a research student to have the following characteristics:

1) sentence construction skills; 2) integrity of thought; 3) justification; 4) logical sequence.

Obviously, a student who fails to compose a sentence will not be able to express himself. This will ultimately undermine the objectivity and originality of the research. The opinions of others will be repeated here, they will be reflected in the sources, and there will be no creative approach. Therefore, sentence construction skills are very important.

One of the most important features of a research student is integrity of opinion. Integrity of thought allows a clearer understanding of the nature of the problem under study, the research process, the results obtained, creates a favorable basis for reflecting existing realities and determining future prospects.

The research student should be able to substantiate this or that issue in the research process, try to substantiate the work to be done or the result obtained, the idea put forward. Rationale is related to the problem, the relevance of the research, goals and objectives, content, expected results and the explanation, conceptual interpretation of this or that idea reflected in the research as a whole. If any of the ideas put forward are not substantiated, then a certain shortcoming in the quality of research is obvious.

One of the important features for a researcher is the ability to take into account the logical sequence. This is directly related to the research process itself, as well as to the research work he wrote on the basis of the research, and to the content of the work he created.

It is important to present the issues in a logical sequence in accordance with the goals and objectives of the research work (this applies not only to the dissertation, master's dissertation, but also to the content of articles, theses, abstracts, reports for conferences). For example, depending on the approach to events and processes (general in particular, or specific in general), the sequence of cause-and-effect relationships increases the quality of research.

Sometimes the logical sequence is not taken into account in the scientific interpretation of any issue in the abstracts submitted by students, and sometimes in the report prepared for the conference as a result of research, or in the article (also found in dissertations, master's dissertations). For example, when it comes to the defining, teaching, and testing stages of an experiment, not waiting for consistency is one of the aspects that undermines the scientific significance of research. The difficulties of some students in this area are clearly felt. Failure to expect a logical sequence in the research work can lead to negative perceptions in the reader about the content of the work, the system, the objective investigation of the problem that needs to be solved, the completeness of scientific results. Therefore, this opinion should ensure the logical continuity of the work carried out in the course of research, a strong connection between events and processes, the realization of the developmental function.

In order to form a research culture in students, it is important that each student knows the following requirements for the quality of research and acts on the basis of these requirements:

1. Achieving completeness of research content. This requirement means taking into account the scope, breadth and richness of the research topic, the correct definition of the problem to be studied.

2. Taking into account the accuracy of the study. According to this student, the researcher must be able to choose the facts that make up the basic concepts of the research subject, understanding the important provisions, while approaching the conclusion without making any mistakes.

3. Fairness of research. This requirement is related to the ability to communicate with the various parties involved in the study, to be in the right position in solving all issues. The requirement of fairness is also important to ensure the objectivity of the scientific results to be obtained.

4. Depth of research. This is one of the most important requirements for a researcher. Thus, in order to reach a more effective, serious scientific conclusion in the research, there is a need for a deeper study of the cause-and-effect relationships of the essence of the problem under study. At the same time, the opportunities to come to an objective scientific conclusion expand, and the theoretical and practical significance of the research increases significantly.

5. Consciousness of research. According to this student, the researcher must be sure of the accuracy of the facts and provisions used in the research process, and be able to argue them. Experience shows that sometimes young researchers, especially students, use it without being sure of the accuracy of the facts and provisions related to the problem they are researching, and thus have difficulty in coming to the right conclusion. Therefore, any fact or provision should be taken seriously, and special attention should be paid to who published it, where it was published, and whether the fact was distorted.

6. The science of research. This requirement is one of the conditions that significantly affect the quality of research work. Thus, the research work should contain serious analysis of the problem, substantiate what new provisions have been put forward as a result of the implementation of the goals and objectives. Therefore, research should be conducted on a scientific basis and areas of application should be identified.

7. Summary of research. This requirement underscores the need for consistency and systematic consideration in research. Thus, the dynamics of the study of the problem in the research work, the process of development towards the result must be clearly given.

8. Application of research results in practice. According to the scientific results obtained for this student, the researcher must be able to develop certain recommendations for use in practice, as well as ways to benefit from it in practice.

Principles of formation of research culture in students

Forming a research culture in students is one of the most important problems of modern competency-based education. The formation of such a culture in today's students is one of the important conditions for their preparation for life as highly qualified specialists. Therefore, it is important to pay serious attention to the solution of this issue in the educational process in higher education institutions and outside the classroom. However, the formation of a research culture must be based on science. From this point of

view, it is possible to carry out such work purposefully, guided by certain principles.

It should be noted that in the scientific literature, along with the concept of "research culture", there are also the concepts of research skills, (or competencies) "research skills". [Belyalova MA 2016; Bustanov HA, Aminova NI 2017; Nosaeva IV 2001; Ponomarchuk PN 2011]

The core of each of these concepts is "skills", "skills development" and "research skills development". The scope of research culture is wider, as it reflects skills as well as moral attitudes.

Approaches to the principles of forming a research culture in students in the scientific literature are different. [Anisimova VA, Nain AA 2012; Seredenko PV 2011]. For example, in the research of VAAnisimova and AANayn, the principles in terms of the problem are expressed as follows:

- the principle of developing the student's ability to manage himself and then others in order to act as an independent and creative specialist in the future;
- the principle of turning the student from a hesitant and executive position to an active subject;
- the principle of stimulating research processes;
- the principle of pedagogical reflection;
- The principle of modeling of scientific research. [Anisimova VA, Nain AA 2012]

VI Andreev and PN Ponomarchuk consider it expedient to give preference to the following principles in terms of the problem:

- principle of completeness;
- module;
- the principle of professional guidance;
- Principle of creativity. [Andreev VI 2003]

By the principle of completeness, the author means that the teaching material should be in the volume required for the formation of research competencies in students. According to the modular principle, the formation of research competencies on a block-stage basis on the basis of a certain structure is understood.

The principle of professional orientation means conducting research aimed at studying the necessary issues that are useful for the student's future career - the selection of the necessary content.

According to the principle of creativity, the content of educational material should create conditions for active mastering by students, their independent work, the development of creative thinking. [Andreev VI 2003]

Researcher MABelyalova uses the concept of "pedagogical position". He considers it important to base scientific research on the following pedagogical position (principles - IH Jabrailov):

- 1) integrated approach to teaching and research activities;
- 2) unified pedagogical culture in the realization of the problem of students' self-determination and self-development;

- 3) purposefulness in the formation and development of students' research qualities;
 - 4) y humanistic and personality-oriented interactions in the process of conducting research;
 - 5) Systematic development of students' creative potential: participation in joint innovative projects, scientific-practical conferences and other events;
 - 6) Democracy, collegiality, openness, readiness for cooperation.
- [Belyalova MA 2016]

Although there are different approaches to the formation of research culture in scientific research, the general direction and essence are basically the same. The goal is for students to have a high level of competence by mastering research qualities and values. Thus, he is able to work with different sources, analyze, compare, generalize, draw conclusions, make appropriate proposals, but also critically approach the problem he studies, the opinions of other experts, substantiate and creatively develop his author's position, to existing scientific ideas and their authors. It can be said that a culture of research is formed in a person who respects and is able to appreciate other moral values.

Experience shows that one of the necessary principles in the formation of a culture of research in students is the provision that they have a scientific way of thinking or creative-research thinking. Because the objective analysis of any issue, the achievement of the right scientific result is first of all directly related to scientific thinking, creative thinking. No matter how rich the material, no matter how many sources, if there is no scientific thinking, no creative thinking, then the research will be far from scientific content, analysis and generalization, lack of logical, critical and creative thinking will not lead to the right results. Therefore, the student must develop scientific thinking, philosophical, historical, pedagogical, and psychological and other issues. must be able to approach from the point of view, know the methodology of research.

Another principle in the formation of a research culture is to determine the mechanism of action. What is meant by the principle of determining the mechanism of action of students? As a rule, before carrying out any work, a general plan is drawn up, the sequence of work is noted, and the work to be done is determined step by step. In short, what is the mechanism of action? how? Under what conditions is it studied? Answers questions broadly, determines the direction of research and the nature of the problem.

Another principle is the independence of students. This principle is primarily aimed at ensuring their personal independence. Although he receives certain recommendations from the teacher, he must work alone to solve the problem, come to a certain conclusion only at the expense of his own thinking, conduct a search himself, and the result should be justified as his personal-author's position. Experience has shown that in some cases, young researchers - students, when substantiating their views on the problem they are researching, only bring to the fore the views of another author or authors, and here the personal-author position is not clear. Or those ideas are presented as the author's position. However, the researcher must analyze the views and

ideas on the problem, express a creative attitude to them, and finally summarize his conclusions.

As another principle, the teacher factor can be accepted in the formation of research culture in students. Thus, even if the student works freely in the research process, it is important that the teacher - the supervisor guides him, assesses the progress of the research as a whole, the importance of the results obtained. Taking into account fairness, mutual respect and objectivity in student-teacher cooperation in this process has a positive effect on increasing the scientific value of research results. However, experience shows that sometimes the teacher does not give the necessary direction and advice to his student's research, which creates difficulties in the research process, the analysis and the results obtained are not generalized correctly. This, in turn, has a negative impact on the formation of a research culture in students. Therefore, the teacher-scientific guiding factor is shown as an important principle in the formation of research culture in students.

The teacher must create favorable conditions for the self-realization of students' creative potential. For example, the participation of students in scientific-practical conferences, seminars, scientific discussions with teachers during the school year gives good results. At this time, the student develops scientific thinking, a culture of controversy, the ability to analyze and generalize, to defend their ideas and other necessary qualities. These are important components of a research culture.

Opportunities and ways to form a research culture in the requirements

In modern times, state policy in the field of education, including new educational programs, opens wide opportunities for the formation of a culture of research in students. The formation of research skills in students is an important requirement in educational programs. Today, the quality of staff training in universities also depends on the level of formation of a research culture in students. Experience shows that sometimes the oral mastering of program materials is satisfied with the students' oral answers in the learning process, seminars, not enough attention is paid to the organization of independent work of students, conducting research work with them. This, in turn, has a negative impact on quality assurance in specialist training.

All subjects taught in universities have the opportunity to form a research culture in students. The subject of pedagogy, first of all, provides information about the essence of the concepts of "research", "research culture" from the theoretical point of view, the need for students to form moral qualities in terms of the problem. In this regard, it is important that students master the theoretical knowledge. The content of subject programs and textbooks developed for universities creates opportunities for the formation of a research culture of students. The effective organization of work in terms of problems in lectures and seminars, extracurricular activities has a positive impact on the development of students' research skills.

The formation of a research culture is an ongoing process. First of all, it is important to know where to start. To do this, the student can ask himself the following question: What will be investigated? For what purpose will it be

investigated? How will it be investigated? What can be the expected result? What is the significance of the problem to be investigated? What can be expected from the research? and so on. Asking these questions and thinking about them will help you find the key elements of the research and guide the research in the right direction.

Seminars play an important role in shaping the research culture of students in the learning process. Seminars open a wide range of research opportunities by focusing on the teaching of a specific subject. For example, in the process of teaching the history of Azerbaijan in higher education, it is possible to conduct various aspects of research on the textbook text, primary sources, historical materials, literary and artistic documents.

It is the knowledge gained as a result of research that allows the studied event or process to be remembered more strongly, but also to be objective. Experience shows that it is possible to learn any topic from a textbook or research material of a specific author, to get information about the events and processes in question. However, if the student looks at the subject from the researcher's point of view, then he can focus on the depths of the problem. For example, when studying the topic "Azerbaijan Democratic Republic", it is important for the student to first research the primary sources on this topic, to study the published materials on the history of the republic. By researching the sources, the student finds answers to a number of questions:

1. What was the political situation in the South Caucasus at the beginning of 1918?
2. What are the characteristics of the historical conditions of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic?
3. What are the factors determining the establishment of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic?
4. What was the purpose of the genocide committed by Armenians against the Turkish-Muslim population?
5. Why was it not possible to protect the independence of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic?
6. On what principles did the Popular Front prefer to build relations with neighboring countries?
7. How do you assess the contribution of the founders of the Popular Front of Azerbaijan MA Rasulzade, FXKhoyski, AM Topchubashov, N. Yusifbeyli and others to the history of Azerbaijan's statehood?
8. With what facts can you explain the great importance of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic to human rights and freedoms?
9. How do you assess the activity of Mohammad Hasan Hajinski in the parliament of the Popular Front Party on the basis of sources?

To find answers to these questions, the student can use a variety of sources and various literature. Answering these questions on the basis of sources, researching the problem is possible in seminar classes, as well as outside the classroom.

The analysis of the following sources of the period of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic (1918-1920) is important for in-depth study of the problem:

1. Legislative documents of the AXC period;
 - Declaration of Independence of May 28, 1918;
 - Resolutions of the National Council of June 17, 1918;
 - "Law of the National Council on the Establishment of the Parliament of Azerbaijan";
 - Law on Azerbaijani Citizenship;
 - Press Charter;
 - Law on the establishment of Baku University;
 - Law on the establishment of diplomatic missions of Azerbaijan in France, Great Britain, Switzerland, Italy, the United States, Russia and Poland.
2. Foreign policy acts;
3. Clerical documents: Documents of the National Council, Parliament and the Cabinet of Ministers. Minutes of parliamentary sessions;
4. Statistical sources;
5. Documents of political parties and public organizations;
6. AXC period press;
7. Documents of personal origin: memoirs, diaries, correspondence, etc.

Along with these sources, it is important to use the Encyclopedia of the People's Republic of Azerbaijan, reports and speeches of national leader Heydar Aliyev, President Ilham Aliyev, their relevant decrees and orders, the works of scientists conducting research on this period²⁰. [Encyclopedia of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic. 2004; Encyclopedia of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic. 2005]

Experience shows that such an approach to the problem under study, or from books and articles from various aspects of research materials plays an important role in objectively revealing the essence of the problem. At the same time, there are ample opportunities for the correct tracking of events and processes, the consideration of sequence connections, a logical approach to the issues of time, space and personality from a historical point of view. The researcher is able to make a comparison on this or that issue, to compare the facts, to study the cause-and-effect relationships, and, as a result, to evaluate his scientific conclusion.

Based on the materials researched, the student concludes that the historical conditions during the establishment of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic were very complicated. During this period, the influence of Soviet Russia on the events in the South Caucasus, the genocide of Bolshevik, Dashnak and other anti-Azerbaijani forces in Azerbaijan against the Turkish-Muslim population, the policy of complete expulsion and destruction of Azerbaijanis from their

²⁰ Aliyev HA Our independence is eternal. Electronic collection <http://heydaraliyev.preslib.az/musteq.html>

Aliyev I.H. Development is our goal. Electronic collection <http://ilhamaliyev.preslib.az/>

native lands aggravated the situation in the region. It was during this period that, as a result of the selflessness of the national-minded sons of the Fatherland, the people united under one flag - around the idea of national independence and created the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic. The government of the People's Republic of Azerbaijan, which declared its independence in Tbilissi (Georgia) and for a time in Ganja and then in Baku, was able to fulfill with honor in such a complex and difficult situation very important tasks. Azerbaijan's state attributes have been created, Azerbaijani Turkish has been formalized as the state language, a democratic parliament has been formed that can serve as an example for the world, a national army has been created, important steps have been taken to improve the defense system to ensure territorial integrity. Serious work was done. The Azerbaijan Democratic Republic, which was recognized as independent on January 11, 1920, was invaded by Soviet Russia and the 11th Army in the spring of the same year and lost its independence.

Despite its short existence - 23 months, the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic has left deep, indelible traces in the history of our statehood.

During these years (1918-1920) a new stage in the history of Azerbaijani statehood - the republican stage was laid. As the first democratic republic in the Muslim East, the APC, as a secular state, attached great importance to human rights and freedoms.

Unfortunately, this republic did not last long.

It is clear from the research that the training dates back to the period of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic

The richness of the materials provides a favorable basis for in-depth research and study of the topic, analysis, comparison, generalization and evaluation of the facts.

From this point of view, it is important for students to get acquainted with these training materials and work independently on relevant historical sources. Experience shows that such a scientific-methodological approach to the problem increases the activity of students, provides them with the formation of the necessary skills on the subject.

The result

Thus, referring to the results of scientific research, we can say that the culture of research is important as a component of the new content of competency-based education. Research culture can also be characterized as a valuable skill and has a significant impact on improving the quality of teaching. Modern educational programs provide ample opportunities for students to form a culture of research. creates a favorable basis for creative approaches from a theoretical and practical point of view, to ensure purposefulness in the formation of a mature personality. It is important that teachers in higher education institutions pay special attention to this issue, taking into account the methodological significance of the problem, give priority to innovations in the preparation of educational standards, curricula and programs, try to improve the quality of education, accustom students to creative work and independence.

References

1. Encyclopedia of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic. (2004). in two volumes. 1st volume. Baku, "Leader", 440p.
2. Encyclopedia of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic. (2005). In two volumes. Volume 2. Baku, "Leader", 472p.
3. Aliyev HA Our independence is eternal. Electronic collection <http://heydaraliyev.preslib.az/musteq.html>
4. Aliyev I.H. Development is our goal. Electronic collection <http://ilhamaliyev.preslib.az/>
5. Mammadov FT (2016), Culturology, culture and civilization. Baku, "OL MMC", (p.31), 260 p.
6. Scientific-theoretical problems of modernization of education (published by IH Jabrailov). (2015). Baku, "Translator", (p. 43), 452 p.
7. Andreev VI (2003). Pedagogy: a course for creative development. 3-e izd. Kazan: Center for Innovative Technologies, 608 p.
8. Anisimova VA, Nain AA (2012). Formation of research skills of university students. Bulletin of the Southern Ural State University, №14, (Series: "Education. Pedagogical Sciences", issue 16 , <https://сіберленінка.ru/article/n/formirovanie-issledovatel'skih-umeniy-studentov->
9. Belyalova MA (2016). Development of research culture of students // International Journal of Applied and Fundamental Research . Scientific journal. 2016, №4-1, p.57-58 , <http://applied-researche.ru/ru/article/view?id=8797>
10. Bustanov HA, Aminova NI (2017). Formation of research skills of students on the basis of information technology // Young Scientist, №17, pp.597-599 // [moluch . ru / archive / 148/41781](http://moluch.ru/archive/148/41781)
11. Nosaeva IV Pedagogical conditions for the formation of research culture of students at the initial stage of education. (2001). Abstract dissertation Ph.D. / IV Nosaeva, SPb., 20 p. and so on.)
12. Ponomarchuk PN (2011). Formation of research competence in students of legal specialties // Modern problems of science and education . №5. Electronic scientific journal , <https://www.science-education.ru/article/view?id=4906> .s.24-31
13. Seredenko PV (2011). Formation of research competence in students of pedagogical university // Psychology of teaching. №3, p.24-31